

DECISION-MAKING AND COMMUNICATION SKILLS OF SCHOOL ADMINISTRATORS: ITS IMPACT TO SERVICE QUALITY AND WORKPLACE RELATIONSHIP

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ABSTRACT

New trends in education welcome changes and challenges. There were changes in how the school works particularly in the service quality and the relationship within the workplace as well as the challenges on how the school administrators will decide on the different issues abided by the changes and how it will be communicated to the stakeholders. This study aimed to determine the decision-making skills of school administrators: their implication to service quality and workplace relationship. This study is a descriptive-correlational kind of research in which it uses a survey questionnaire through the use of google form for easier distribution and collection of data. There were 125 teacher-respondents teaching in seven schools in Candelaria East District, Division of Quezon, conducted last March 2021. Based on the result the school administrators are skilled in using their decision and communication skills. The service provided by the school is of high quality while the relationship in the workplace is to a great extent. Based on the findings, how skilled the school administrators in deciding and communicating have an impact on the service quality and workplace relationship. Moreover, it was also found that there were sub-variables with directly predict the service quality provided by the school. Those sub-variables are time management and reasoning under decision-making skills and non-verbal communication skills. The researcher recommends that the school administrators be careful in communicating with the stakeholders as well as in considering when making decisions because these skills can make or break the organization, the service quality provided by the schools, and the relationship within the workplace.

Keywords: Decision-making skills, Communication Skills, Service Quality, Workplace relationship